

Theoretical and solution chemistry of metal complexes of furfural

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Abstract : The interaction between furfural and biologically important metal ions Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} was studied in solution phase through potentiometry and gas phase using *ab initio* HF/6-31G* and MP2/6-31G* methods. Ground state geometries were optimized and tested through frequency analysis. For simplicity 1 : 1 species ratio was considered for the theoretical study. It was found out that furfural is a bidentate ligand and binds through furan oxygen and carbonyl oxygen with the entire four metal ions in the gas and solution phases. The binding effect is found to be in the order : furan oxygen < carbonyl oxygen. The results indicate that furan oxygen binds to the metal ion through s and p_z orbitals, and the carbonyl oxygen binds through s and p_y orbitals. The binding effects and modes of both the oxygens are found to differ. Furfural forms high spin complex with Co^{II} and Ni^{II} with the multiplicity of 4 and 3 respectively. The strength of Cu^{II} -furfural binding in both gas and solution phases is found to be lesser than expected. This may be due to the weak binding effect of furan oxygen. The results demonstrate that the order of binding in solution phase is $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} < \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} < \text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$.

Keywords : Theoretical study, solution study, metal complexes, furfural.

Furfural is a well known natural compound used extensively in food, fuel and paint industries¹⁻³. Schiff base complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} involving furfural and 2-aminopyridine, ethylenediamine, diethylenetriamine, dipropylenetriamine, spermidine, hydrazine, chloroaniline or 2-aminopyridine have been found to have antibacterial and antifungal activities⁴⁻⁹. Schiff base of furfural and anthranilic acid can act as antitumor agent¹⁰. The present study reveals the interaction between furfural and the 3d-metal ions such as Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} .

Experimental

The General Atomic and Molecular Electronic Structure System (GAMESS) program^{11,12} was employed for the *ab initio* (HF) calculations made in this study. The 6-31G* basis set¹³ was used. Binary stability constants were determined by potentiometric method at $27 \pm 1^\circ \text{C}$ and 0.1μ ionic strength. Initial geometry of the molecule was constructed from the standard geometry of furfural. The conformational search was carried out along the a-axis at 180° . All the semiempirical calculations were carried out by MOPAC 6 program^{14,15}.

Results and discussion

In order to have a clear understanding about the metal

complexes of furfural, it is necessary to optimize its ground state equilibrium geometry. A systematic conformational study can help to provide a clear understanding of the energy and often important insights into equilibrium geometry. The conformers and the energy profile of furfural along the a-axis are shown in Fig. 1.

Considering the different structures for the molecule, there might be several possible structures arising from rotation around the $\text{C}_4\text{-C}_6$ bond.

The calculated relative conformational energy values, however, are often sensitive to the method used in the calculations. In order to obtain the lowest energy conformer for the furfural the calculations were done at the RHF/6-31G* and MP2/6-31G*. On the basis of these methods it is able to distinguish among the conformers with significantly lower energy *trans* furfural (Fig. 1). The relative energy difference of the studied conformers *cis* and *trans* furfural is in the order of 2 kcal/ mol.

The energy profile is almost symmetrical. The perpendicular conformer is in the top of the barrier. The planar conformers are stable than non-planar conformers. For this system it was observed that the calculated barrier height is very large for the free rotation of aldehyde group, suggesting that furfural is a rigid molecule. The rotational

Fig. 1. Conformers and metal complexes of furfural.

barrier is due to loss of symmetry, loss of electron delocalization and non-bonded interaction between aromatic electron cloud of furan ring and carbonyl oxygen in furfural.

Relative distribution among the population of *cis* and *trans* conformers is 1 : 1. The calculated dipole moment values of the conformers show that the *cis* conformer has the higher dipole moment than *trans*. It has been reported that, conformer with higher dipole moment exist in the solid and solution phases¹⁶. Thus it has been concluded that the *trans* conformer is the theoretically expected one and the *cis* form exists in solid and solution phases. Since our studies are made in solution, the *cis* conformer only is considered for the present study. Further, NMR studies have documented that furfural exists in *cis* conformation in liquid^{17,18}.

Important geometrical parameters are given in Table 1. A good correlation exists between the computed and experimental geometrical parameters. It is emphasized that the bond angles have a mean deviation of 0–3°. From the experimental values the C–C and C–O single bond lengths are determined to be 1.432 Å and 1.376 Å. The C=C and C=N have a double bond length of 1.346 Å and 1.309 Å respectively for 2-furfuraldoxime¹⁹. Taking in to account the effect of conjugation, the calculated values of the *cis*-furfural molecule is in reasonable agreement with the above mentioned experimental data. So the calculated values of *cis*-furfural are very reasonable. The

Table 1. Important geometrical parameters of M^{II}-*cis*-furfural

Parameters	Co ^{II} - <i>cis</i> -furfural	Ni ^{II} - <i>cis</i> -furfural	Cu ^{II} - <i>cis</i> -furfural	Zn ^{II} - <i>cis</i> -furfural
Bond length (Å)				
C ₁ -C ₂	1.3367	1.3360	1.4170	1.3365
C ₂ -O ₃	1.4030	1.4053	1.3296	1.4049
O ₃ -C ₄	1.4372	1.4390	1.3706	1.4394
C ₄ -C ₅	1.3535	1.3532	1.4262	1.3549
C ₄ -C ₆	1.4072	1.4080	1.4756	1.4064
C ₆ -O ₇	1.2671	1.2678	1.2153	1.2710
M-O ₃	2.0594	2.0090	4.5682	2.0090
Bond angle (°)				
C ₂ -O ₃ -C ₄	110.0236	109.8865	110.2992	109.9094
O ₃ -C ₄ -C ₅	105.8890	105.9692	108.0306	106.0050
O ₃ -C ₄ -C ₆	108.1988	108.0795	108.2245	107.9755
C ₄ -C ₆ -O ₇	112.8944	113.0361	119.2253	113.4593
M-O ₃ -C ₄	110.1334	109.3111	76.5915	108.2349
Dihedral angle (°)				
C ₁ -C ₂ -O ₃ -C ₄	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
C ₂ -O ₃ -C ₄ -C ₅	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
C ₂ -O ₃ -C ₄ -C ₆	180.0000	180.0000	180.0000	180.0000
O ₃ -C ₄ -C ₆ -O ₇	180.0000	180.0000	180.0000	180.0000

molecule is planar with no imaginary frequency and it has C_s symmetry.

Among the *ab initio* calculations, MP2 level has lesser charge density for atoms than HF. This is due to the higher electron correlation of MP2 over HF. The O₃ and O₇ are the higher negative centers for protonation and complexation.

Mulliken atomic orbital population analysis shows an increase in electron population of the p_z and a decrease in the population of the p_x and p_y orbitals on the O₃ due to aromatization of furfural. In the semiempirical methods s -orbital has more population and p_x orbital has more electron density than p_y in O₃. But it is in reverse in *ab initio* methods. This may be due to the electron delocalization observed in the *ab initio* methods. In O₇ atom the s and p_y orbital have more population in AM1 and PM3 methods. RHF and MP2 have more population in the p_x orbital. The results reveal that the coordination sites O₃ and O₇ possess different characters.

Because of the computational expense of *ab initio* calculations the number of atoms which can be included is limited and so that the use of *ab initio* methods is restricted to the complexation of single *cis*-furfural ligand only and not for water molecules.

It was observed that *cis*-furfural has two electronegative atoms, furfural (O₃) and carboxyl (O₇) oxygens. Therefore *cis*-furfural either binds monodentately through O₃ or O₇ oxygen or in bidentate mode through both O₃ and O₇ oxygens with metal ions. In order to find out the mode of binding of M^{II} with *cis*-furfural its HF energy values are calculated (Table 2). The structures are given in Fig. 1. It was found that the bidentate mode of binding is preferred. The binding energy is in the order : O₃ and O₇ > O₇ > O₃. The less binding energy of monodentate O₃ than O₇ is due to the aromatization of O₃ electrons. Thus *cis*-furfural is a bidentate ligand and binds M^{II} through furfural (O₃) and carbonyl (O₇) oxygens.

It is expected that the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} form complexes with different multiplicities. The relative energy values for multiplicities of Co^{II}/Ni^{II}-*cis*-furfural are given in Table 3. The Co^{II}/Ni^{II}-*cis*-furfural complexes with multiplicity of four and three are more stable than multiplicity of two and one respectively. This implies that Co^{II}/Ni^{II}-*cis*-furfural complexes are high spin.

The bond angle M-O₃-C₄ for Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} are 110.1334°, 109.3111°, 76.5915° and 108.2349° respectively. Thus it has been concluded that Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} form tetrahedral geometry with one molecule of fur-

Table 2. Mode of binding of M^{II}-*cis*-furfural complexes

Metal ion	RHF/6-31G* (Hartree/mol) (Energy of free metal ion)		
	O ₃ and O ₇	O ₃	O ₇
Co	-1722.0916 (-341.5485)	-1719.4925	-1719.6922
Ni	-1847.5563 (-341.5689)	-1844.7557	-1847.5041
Cu	-1979.6189 (-341.5828)	-1976.7393	-1979.5646
Zn	-2118.4573 (-341.5727)	-2118.3694	-2118.4072

Table 3. Relative multiplicity energies of Co^{II}/Ni^{II}-*cis*-furfural

	RHF/6-31G* (Energy) (Hartree/mol)			
	Co ^{II}		Ni ^{II}	
	Mult. 2	Mult. 4	Mult. 1	Mult. 3
	-1719.4843	-1722.0916	-1847.4524	-1847.5562

fural. Cu^{II} forms square planar in 1 : 1 complex with furfural.

In solution all the four metal ions form MA and MA₂ types of complexes with furfural in addition to HA species. The log K_{10} values are 1.81, 2.02, 2.69 and 1.74 log units respectively for Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} metal ions-furfural complexes. These values are comparable with the stability constant values of complexes of furansemicarbazones, in which the ligands are bidentate and bind through furfural and carbonyl oxygens²⁰. It has been concluded that furfural behaves as a bidentate ligand and binds through furfural oxygen and carbonyl group of the aldehyde with all the four metal ions. Bryson and Dwyer²¹ potentiometrically studied a number of metal complexes of β -furfuraldoximates and found that the ligands bind through furfural and hydroxyl oxygens. In the solid complexes of furansemicarbazones, the furfural oxygen also takes part in the coordination²⁰.

The strength of Cu^{II}-furfural binding in both gas and solution phases is found to be lesser than expected. This may be due to the weak binding effect of furan oxygen. The stability of binding in solution phase follows Irving-William²² order : Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II} > Zn^{II}.

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